

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
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Project acronym:	IMPULSE
Project name:	IMProving User experience, Long-term sustainability and Services of EU-OPENSSCREEN

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Executive summary

The EU-OPENSSCREEN Research Infrastructure, a leading European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) for chemical biology and early drug discovery (<https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/>), offers services in high-throughput compound screening and medicinal chemistry to both academic and industrial users. As such, EU-OPENSSCREEN is pivotal in advancing early-stage drug discovery in Europe. To meet the growing complexity of modern drug discovery research, EU-OPENSSCREEN has recently expanded its services to include fragment-based drug discovery and chemoproteomics. The IMPULSE project will further enhance EU-OPENSSCREEN by developing and integrating new services in AI/ML, novel chemical modalities and cutting-edge cell models combined with CRISPR-Cas9/RNAi-based genetic screening. Additionally, IMPULSE will implement standardised operational and data practices to improve reproducibility and data quality, while tailored outreach and training programmes will increase both awareness of the EU-OPENSSCREEN's activities and the operational excellence of the ERIC. These efforts, along with new partnerships with industry and charities, will ensure the long-term sustainability and accessibility of EU-OPENSSCREEN's comprehensive service portfolio.

This Data Management Plan specifies the datasets that will be collected, used, and re-used during the IMPULSE project, detailing how data will be handled both during and after the project. It outlines the methodologies and standards to be applied, as well as the measures for preserving data beyond the IMPULSE completion. A list of IMPULSE work-packages is available as appendix.

1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

All data will be novel as they will be generated from emerging and innovative technologies.

For WP6, data will be collected from available datasets to build the machine learning model. BBB037, BBBC022, and BBBC036 databases contain data relating to Cell Painting and the ChEMBL database (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl/>) contains activity data relating to small molecules. Internal data from EU-OPENSSCREEN members will also be used to validate the generated model on unseen data.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The types and formats of data will mostly be numerical, including those from WP4 for new chemical modalities, all of which are compatible for deposition in EU-OPENSSCREEN's European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD, <https://ecbd.eu/>). For WP6, the ChEMBL bioactive molecule database with drug-like properties will be downloaded as a CSV file. This database is highly annotated with chemical, bioactivity and genomic data of molecules.

The Cell Painting assays will produce 2D image data (different fields of view and different channels/detection wavelengths) in TIFF files. The extracted morphological profiles will be numerical data in a CSV file. In WP6, analysis of these files will be performed using Python scripts, and the output will predict relevant on-target modulation and cellular signaling pathways, in the form of a CSV file. The machine learning tool will use LSTM to encode the ChEMBL SMILES data. A convolutional neural network (EfficientNet) will encode the image information. Finally, a graph neural network will produce molecule graphs from the encoded SMILES also encoding physicochemical information. This information will then be passed to a dense layer to generate the final prediction.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To support EU-OPENSSCREEN in keeping and expanding a leading position as a platform for the discovery of novel chemical probes and drugs and to strengthen Europe's excellent position in chemical biology and drug discovery. Update and expand the EU-OPENSSCREEN service offerings with emerging technologies, improve service quality and data accessibility and broaden its user base. These activities will be managed and aligned with FAIR principles as an essential component.

ECBD (operated by the Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences (IMG)) and OwnCloud (operated by Fraunhofer ITMP) will store all generated datasets. Data will be accessible to the scientific community upon the open access principles. Before the data go public, they will undergo necessary process of validation and inspection and only then they will be released to the scientific community.

Cell Painting of EU-OPENSSCREEN's European Academic Compound Library (EACL, <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/compound-collection/european-academic-compound-library-eacl.html>) compounds delivers an unbiased and in-depth characterization of the biological activity of these compounds. The generated data with the high content image data as well as the extracted morphological profiles will be provided free and open source to the scientific community in dedicated repositories.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The size of one assay data point should preferably not exceed 10 MB. The size of the entire generated Cell Painting image data will be in multiple terabyte range. The generated raw single cell profiles as well as processed and aggregated profile ranging in multiple gigabytes.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Data will be generated by the IMPULSE project partners. Cell Painting data based on the EACL is generated at the Institute of Molecular and Translational Medicine (IMTM), Czech Republic. Image data will be processed at the Leibniz-Forschungsinstitut für Molekulare Pharmakologie (FMP).

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data will be useful to academic and industry researchers and broad scientific community enabling more efficient and effective collaboration between them. Specific areas of research will include deconvolution of modes of action of small molecules with biological interest using innovative advanced cell and disease models, RNAi/CRISPR and functional screening techniques, new chemical modalities, artificial Intelligence and machine learning tools. The Cell Painting data based on the EACL will be useful to academic and industry researchers engaged in drug discovery and chemical biology as this data adds a broad and unbiased characterization of these compounds in cell-lines highly relevant to drug discovery research.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Compounds will be identified by persistent and unique EOS numbers, which will be designed by ECBD staff. Compounds have reserved intervals from EOS1 to EOS299999. Compounds will be linked by Unichem database especially to PubChem and ChEMBL.

Research data may be linked to the corresponding publications via DOI and in publications can be referenced via EOS.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Each assay will be described with necessary metadata as creator, measurement and upload dates, validation and description of how and for which biological target the assay was measured.

Unique EOS numbers will be assigned to compounds, assays and biological targets. The EOS number will be persistent, and the use of DOI is planned only for publications. Naming conventions will be derived from ontologies, i.e. for taxonomy and biological targets, and ontology terms.

The Cell Painting image data, raw single-cell profiles, and processed profiles will be linked to the persistent identifier of the ECBD (EOS number). The uploaded data at the respective repositories will be identified via a persistent unique identifier.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Ontology terms and their synonyms will serve as search keywords.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Assay data will be uploaded with a creation day/timestamp and the corresponding validation information. Revisions will be made as necessary as a new assay and uploaded with the same EOS number. The old assay data will be accessible under the same EOS number but with deprecation mark (URL will be with suffix).

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

A geographical back-up will serve to provide data security.

Authentication, authorization, and access through HTTPS will enable security of sensitive data.

Cell Painting image data, raw single cell profiles and processed aggregated profiles will be uploaded to dedicated image and data repositories such as the Cell Painting Gallery (Weisbart et al. 2024) and Bioimage Archive (Hartley et al. 2022). The aggregated profiles will also be uploaded onto the ECBD.

All scripts produced in WP6 will be made available through GitHub.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

The ECBD is the current informatics platform for data collection, storage, annotation, and sharing with users funded by and executed under the agreed operational plan of the EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC. The ECBD is operated by IMG, an official, high-capacity EU-OPENSSCREEN screening partner site and the database hosting partner site of the EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC.

There is an ongoing active collaboration with the Cell Painting Gallery with a first Cell Painting dataset being hosted on the ECBD. The collaboration with the Bioimage archive is in the first phase and will move into a practical implementation of uploading the first dataset in the next half a year.

In addition, GitHub is a reliable repository for storing the produced scripts, which can be made private if desired.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Through the ECBD, EU-OPENSSCREEN provides well-annotated, standardized, controlled datasets with comprehensive coverage of both chemical and biological information to the broad scientific community. Specifically, the ECBD represents an important public data resource to support scientists in the fields of chemical biology and drug discovery, including medicinal chemists, bioinformaticians and cheminformaticians. This comprehensive coverage complements and extends upon existing public bioactivity datasets. Such large-scale open-access data are the basis for computational data integration which can provide a systematic overview of the data and allow for the prediction of drug-target interactions, networks, adverse effects, and drug combinations.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

The ECBD data are publicly accessible without any restrictions of use (Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>)).

Cell Painting data are also publicly accessible without any restrictions of use via the CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0) (<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/deed.en>)).

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

To protect research intellectual property rights, uploading partner sites can set an embargo period of up to 3 years for new assay data.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

The data are accessible according to the open access principles, and public data can be accessed by default without any login credentials or user accounts.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

The 3-year embargo period for new assay data can be prolonged for up to an additional 3 years (6 years in total) for a fee. Assay data which are not yet validated or are under embargo can only be accessed by authorized users (e.g., data uploaders and chemists who submitted academic compounds to the EACL). However, authorized users only see data for their submitted compounds. Metadata will be accessible without restrictions and released with associated biological and chemical data. After data validation, and once the grace period is over, there are no additional access restrictions.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

The ECBD and Cell Painting data will be accessible according to the open access principles, and public data can be accessed by default without login credentials or user accounts.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

All validated data will be publicly available after the grace period; therefore, a data access committee is not necessary.

Metadata:***Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?***

The ECBD and Cell Painting data are public and accessible without any restrictions of use.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

The ECBD server will be operated by IMG at least 2 years after the end of the project. Access to the Cell Painting data is provided via external collaboration partners independent of this project.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?

Relevant software (Postgres and RDKit) is open source and not necessary for data manipulation. For Cell Painting data no proprietary data formats will be used such that data can be accessed and read with open-source software platforms.

2.3. Making data interoperable***What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?***

The standard ontologies will describe assay data, and units will be also specified by ontology. Chemical structures will be described by SMILES, InChI and Mol files.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or

extending them?

Uploaders will be able to use customized numerical values and ECBD staff will try to link them to existing ontology, modify them internally or expand them externally after consultation with their generators and authors.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

All data will be novel and qualified references will not be necessary.

2.4. Increase data re-use**How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**

Data will be accessible under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>). The Cell Painting analysis will be shared on public repositories via Github and provided via the MIT license (<https://opensource.org/license/mit>).

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

The ECBD data are public and accessible without any restrictions of use. The data are accessible according to the open access principles, and public data can be accessed by default without any login credentials or user accounts. Additionally, the public subset of the database is also accessible as CSV, xlsx, and json files for each type of data (assays, targets, and compounds) or as the PostgreSQL database dump; however, the latter is not intended for general usage, as it requires advanced knowledge of PostgreSQL database technology. Relevant software tools (PostgreSQL and RDKit Cheminformatics Framework) are open source and are not necessary for data manipulation. The Cell Painting data and analysis will be made available free and open source.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

The data produced will be useable by third parties. The data will be stored and usable independently of the project, until the ECBD is operated. The Cell Painting data and analysis will be hosted on external repositories independent of this project.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The standard ontologies will describe assay data, units will be also specified by ontology. Chemical structures will be described by SMILES, InChI and Mol files.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

The data will be checked automatically during the upload process and manually by ECBD staff, the uploaders and their collaborators.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

To improve data security, interoperability, and reuse, a subset of public bioactivity data from the ECBD was deposited into the ChEMBL database, which collects a wide range of assay data from many sources. The ECBD structure reflects all ChEMBL data/metadata fields (both mandatory and optional), and an automated file-based export of curated data to ChEMBL has been implemented in accordance with ChEMBL requirements.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

During assay data upload will be annotated by data uploader with ontologies. Online research data repositories will be considered depending on the types and formats of the data generated and collected. Some examples of relevant repositories for specific datasets include:

- Assay data: PubChem BioAssay (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/docs/bioassays>).
- BioAssayOntology (<http://bioassayontology.org/>).
- BRENDA (<https://www.brenda-enzymes.org/>).
- Cellosaurus (<https://web.expasy.org/cellosaurus/>).
- ChEMBL Drug Target subset (<http://geneontology.org/docs/go-subset-guide/>).
- Genomic data: EBI (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>)/DDBJ (<https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/index-e.html>), or NCBI GenBank (<https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/>). These are equivalent and synced with each other.
- Genomic data (raw): NCBI SRA (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>).
- Metagenomic data: EBI MGnify (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics>).
- NIH Taxonomy (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>).
- Spectroscopic NMR data: Chemspider (<https://www.chemspider.com/>) or NP-MRD (<https://np-mrd.org/>).
- Spectroscopic MS data: GNPS (<https://gnps.ucsd.edu/ProteoSAFe/static/gnps-splash.jsp>), Massbank (<https://massbank.eu/MassBank/>) or MASSive (<https://massive.ucsd.edu/ProteoSAFe/static/massive.jsp>).
- Units of Measurement Ontology (<https://github.com/HajoRijgersberg/OM>).
- Structural data: Chemspider (<https://www.chemspider.com/>) or PubChem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>).
- Processed data: GEO (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>).

4. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

The implementation of FAIR principles is covered by the ECBD development contract, therefore minimal additional costs are anticipated for this project. Cell Painting data will be hosted by external public repositories via collaborations. No additional costs will be incurred.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

The costs for the development and hosting of the ECBD and data curation are covered by EU-OPENSREEN ERIC under the agreement with the IMG.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The ECBD is operated by IMG, the database partner site of the EU-OPENSOURCE ERIC. The correctness of uploaded data is the responsibility of the uploader. To ensure further correctness, data is uploaded to intermediate store where are validated by uploader and ECBD staff. The EU-OPENSOURCE Cell Painting team is responsible for the data management of the generated Cell Painting data.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

During the project, bioactive data will be additionally uploaded to ChEMBL database therefore data should be preserved for long term with minimal costs.

Non-public results will be stored locally by each partner according to requirements of local data management plans.

5. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

A geographical back-up will serve to provide data security. Authentication, authorization, and access through HTTPS enable security of sensitive data.

Access to the ECBD servers is only possible via HTTPS. Sensitive data, such as data under embargo and user profiles, are accessible only to authorized users with the proper permissions. Permissions are set by ECBD staff upon request from ERIC and partner sites. The portal is administrated via SSH, and data can only be transferred and stored within a private, secure network at CESNET.

Raw Cell Painting image data will be stored on servers with 2 back-ups at the site that generates the image data. Generated profiles will be stored on servers with 2 back-ups at the site that processed the image data. No sensitive personal or patient data will be generated or stored.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

The ECBD server will be operated by IMG at least 2 years after the end of the project. The Cell Painting data will be hosted by external public repositories.

6. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Research data generated by the partner sites should not raise any ethical concerns. The user login information will not be publicly available.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

IMPULSE is committed to the highest standards of data security and protection to preserve the personal rights and interests of participants.

Personal data are processed in accordance with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Directive 95/46/EC.

The project will not collect or produce any data connected to a person, i.e. "personal data". The data collection is not subject to ethical legislation.

7. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	01.10.2024	Initial version

Appendix

IMPULSE List of work-packages:

WP	Title & short description
1	<p>Long-term sustainability and access procedures: WP1 will ensure EU-OPENSSCREEN RI's sustainability by i) integrating novel services from WP3–6 and establishing access rules, workflows and procedures for these services and ii) expanding its global reach.</p>
2	<p>Creating a repository of community compounds: WP2 aims to incorporate unique novel compounds sourced from the chemistry community, subjecting them to thorough bio-profiling including cell painting.</p>
3	<p>Validating pharmacology using advanced disease models and genetic screens: WP3 aims to develop capabilities and workflows for validating hit bioactive compounds identified from large-screening campaigns using cellular models that accurately represent disease phenotypes. This approach will include analysing the compounds' mechanisms of action (MoA) through complementary genetic screening techniques.</p>
4	<p>New chemical modalities: WP4 aims to develop specialised services for new chemical modalities beyond traditional small molecules which are designed to target challenging targets (e.g., new chemical probes, targeted degraders, enzymatic modulators, multitarget molecules associated to polypharmacology).</p>
5	<p>Data reproducibility and operational standards: WP5 will focus on implementing common operational standards and increasing the quality and reproducibility of EU-OPENSSCREEN RI's data.</p>
6	<p>ML/AI for identification of modes of action with cell painting and small molecule data: WP6 focusses on collecting and preprocessing data to apply deep learning techniques for predicting pathways and drug targets.</p>
7	<p>Training and capacity building: WP7 will enhance training activities, identify and address training needs, and develop training programmes for emerging areas in drug discovery covered in WP3–6.</p>

8	<p>Engagement with public–private initiatives: WP8 aims to identify and map the expertise and capabilities of the consortium's partner sites and disseminate this information to maintain ongoing engagement with industry.</p>
9	<p>Outreach and dissemination: WP9 will effectively communicate the EU-OPENSREEN and IMPULSE's objectives, findings, and impact to diverse stakeholders, including the public, user community, and industry, ensuring broad awareness and engagement.</p>
10	<p>Project management: WP10 works closely with all WPs to ensure smooth and coordinated project operation.</p>
11	<p>Ethics requirements: WP11 sets out the ethics requirements that the project must comply with according to the IMPULSE Grant Agreement.</p>

